

Thermal Stability of Gd_2CuO_4

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The thermal stability of Gd_2CuO_4 as a function of oxygen potential in the gas phase has been studied by thermogravimetry. It is observed that Gd_2CuO_4 decomposes first to an intermediate phase Gd_2CuO_{4-x} and finally to Gd_2O_3 and Cu_2O .

The standard free energy change, $\Delta G_{O_2}^0$ data was derived only from the decomposition steps during heating the mechanism of decomposition and reformation is verified by X-ray diffraction analysis of the products at various stages.

RARE earth copper oxides of the general formula Ln_2CuO_4 were shown to exhibit very interesting electrical properties¹, besides their remarkable catalytic and magnetic behaviour². Rare earth oxides and copper oxides were shown to form compounds of the type Ln_2CuO_4 ¹ ($Ln=La, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd$), $Ln_2'Cu_2O_5$ ³ ($Ln'=Tb, Dy, Er, Yb, Y$) and $Ln''CuO_2$ ($Ln''=La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu$). The standard Gibbs' free energies of formation of the Ln_2CuO_4 and $Ln_2'Cu_2O_5$ were determined by Tretyakov et al³ by oxide electrolyte cell method. These authors³ agreed that $Ln''CuO_2$ compounds were unstable above 1273 K and therefore assumed the phase Cu_2O to be coexisting with Ln_2O_3 , Ln_2CuO_4 or $Ln_2'O_3$, $Ln_2'Cu_2O_5$ in order to fix the oxygen potential in the range 1200-1350 K. However, independent investigations carried out earlier in this laboratory^{4,5} on La_2CuO_4 using similar galvanic cell method over an extensive temperature range (970-1370 K) clearly established the fact that it is $LaCuO_2$ and not Cu_2O that should coexist with La_2O_3 and La_2CuO_4 . Lehuède⁶ et al showed that when La_2CuO_4 is heated under vacuum at 1023 K, a non-stoichiometric phase, La_2CuO_{4-x} , is obtained. Haas and Kordes⁷ reported that Gd_2O_3 did not form $GdCuO_2$ and probably the thermal stability of $LaCuO_2$ decreased from La to Eu such that $GdCuO_2$ could not be formed. Hence a thermogravimetric study of Gd_2CuO_4 in controlled atmosphere was undertaken.

Experimental

Materials: Reagent grade Gd_2O_3 (from Indian Rare Earths) and copper acetate (E. Merck, A.R. grade) were used as starting materials. A coprecipitation followed by solid state reaction method¹ was adopted for the preparation and Gd_2CuO_4 obtained was characterized by X-ray diffraction technique.

Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on Stanton thermobalance (Model HT). Four different oxygen partial pressures in the range 0.0213 to 0.0022 MPa were obtained by appropriate mixing of com-

pressed air and nitrogen through Fisher mixing flowmeters. Flow rates were in the range 2-12 cm^3sec^{-1} . Temperature calibration was carried out by comparison of the CuO decomposition temperatures at different P_{O_2} . Philips X-ray unit, PW 1010 alongwith Diffractometer PW 1051 was used for X-ray diffraction analysis of different products.

Results and Discussion

According to Tretyakov³ Gd_2CuO_4 (or any Ln_2CuO_4) should decompose in air according to the equation (1):

In the case of La_2CuO_4 it was established that the decomposition proceeds^{4,5} according to (2) and (3):

If Gd_2CuO_4 should completely decompose into Gd_2O_3 and Cu_2O , even then percentage weight loss should be less than 2%; this would necessitate taking large amounts (~500 mg) of the sample. However, very large amounts of the sample (2-3 g) though yielded a better measurement of weight loss could introduce serious ambiguities in initiation temperature for the reasons discussed⁸ elsewhere. Normally 500-700 mg sample was used for each run except those intended exclusively for determination of compositions. Gd_2CuO_4 underwent decomposition in two steps (4) and (5):

By taking large amount of sample x was estimated to be 0.30-0.40. Absolute value of the oxygen/metal ratio of the quenched sample of

Gd₂CuO_{4-x} was established by H₂-reduction into Gd₂O₃ and Cu metal using a precise microthermo-balance⁸. The composition was found to be Gd₂CuO_{3.63}.

When the second stage of decomposition is complete, the products were cooled in flowing N₂ (oxygen content 3000 ppm) and characterised by X-ray powder patterns. The products were mainly Cu₂O and Gd₂O₃ with traces of Gd₂CuO₄ (due to reoxidation by oxygen impurity in N₂). The intermediate Gd₂CuO_{4-x} was found to be an entirely new phase hitherto unreported.

The TG runs were taken in both static and flowing air (flowrate 12 cm³sec⁻¹) environment. Understandably flowing air registered 10-15° lower temperatures than static air. Several thermal cycles were conducted on the same sample. The most remarkable feature of this investigation was the high degree of reversibility of the reactions (4) and (5) in oxygen rich environments (at heating or cooling rates of 4-6° min⁻¹). Since cooling curves gave rise to much larger uncertainties in temperature (±20°) compared to heating curves (±10°) only the latter were considered for further evaluation. Table 1 represents the summary of data from those runs which did not show kinetic limitations. It is seen that at the four oxygen partial pressures employed (0.0218, 0.049, 0.0914 and 0.21 in units of 0.101 MPa), the calculated RT ln P_{O₂} showed a fairly linear dependance with temperature (Table 2 and Fig. 1)

Fig. 1 RT ln P_{O₂} vs T Plot for the System

(a) Gd₂CuO₄ → Gd₂CuO_{4-x} (○)
and (b) Gd₂CuO_{4-x} → Gd₂O₃Cu₂O (X)

for both the reactions (4) and (5). Lower oxygen partial pressures (e. g., N₂ with 3000 ppm oxygen) did not yield any useful data owing to kinetic limitations.

The standard Gibb's free energy change for reactions (4) and (5) could be represented by the linear equations (6) and (7) :

TABLE 1
VARIATION OF DISSOCIATION TEMPERATURES
WITH LN P_{O₂}

Volume flow rate dm ³ hour ⁻¹	P _{O₂} (a)	ln P _{O₂}	T ₁ /K	T ₂ /K	
					Air
4.62	40.0	0.0218	-3.83	1263	1373
4.62	15.4	0.049	-3.02	1293	1413
4.62	6.0	0.0914	-2.39	1333	1423
9.0	0.0	0.21	-1.56	1363	1453 ^(b)

TABLE 2
FREE ENERGY DATA FOR Gd₂ CuO₄

T ₁ /K	ΔG°/KJ ^(c)	T ₂ /K	ΔG°/KJ ^(e)
1263	40.2	1373	43.7
1293	32.5	1413	35.5
1333	26.5	1423	28.3
1363	17.7	1453	18.8

(a) With reference to pure oxygen at a pressure of 0.1013 MPa.

(b) In static air, the decomposition temperatures are higher for obvious reasons.

(c) For the reaction producing 1 mole of oxygen.

(d) T₁ and T₂ represent the temperatures of the two decomposition steps.

$$\Delta G_{O_2}^\circ \pm 5/KJ = -323 + 0.225 T \text{ (1263-1363 K) ... (6)}$$

$$\Delta G_{O_2}^\circ \pm 5/KJ = -476 + 0.314 T \text{ (1373-1453 K) ... (7)}$$

Owing to very limited temperature range equations (6) and (7) represented free energy data strictly over the temperature range of experiment; these should not be extrapolated to identify the intercept and slope as enthalpy and entropy changes⁸ respectively especially so for a dynamic technique. However, it is interesting to compare with the only equilibrium measurement available on this system by Tretyakov et al⁸. They measured the emf of the cell

over 1220-1360 K which could be represented by the least square equation (9)

$$E \pm 1/mV = 607.3 - 0.418 T \dots (9)$$

The temperature at which the dissociation pressure of "Gd₂CuO₄" equals P_{O₂} of air, emf of the above cell should be zero. Therefore equation (9) to zero, temperature of dissociation works out to be 1453 K. This extrapolated value (1453 K) is identical with our value (Table 2) for the second reaction (i. e., Gd₂CuO_{4-x} to Gd₂O₃ and Cu₂O). This agreement is of course fortuitous as could be seen by calculation of temperature at which P_{O₂} of the ternary electrode in cell (8) equals 0.0022 MPa

(the lowest P_{O_2} of the present TG study, Table 1) ; it is 1300 K in contradiction with observed values of 1263 and 1363 K quoted in Table 1 for the reactions (4) and (5) respectively. Since equation (9) by Tretykov et al⁸ corresponded to reaction (1) by virtue of their choice of solid phase to fix the P_{O_2} , it [equation (9)] should be an average situation of the equilibria (4) and (5).

To conclude, this investigation clearly established that Gd_2CuO_4 decomposes into Gd_2O_3 and Cu_2O through a new intermediate phase Gd_2CuO_{4-x} which was isolated and characterized using dynamic TG method, the thermodynamic dependence of ambient P_{O_2} (in the range 0.0213 to 0.0022 MPa) on initiation temperature of reactions (4) and (5) could be determined. This compound proves to be one of the rare example of the reversible solid reaction.

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